

Replication and transmission of an influenza A(H3N2) virus harboring the polymerase acidic I38T substitution, in guinea pigs.

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Abstract

The polymerase acidic (PA) I38T substitution is a dominant marker of resistance to baloxavir. We evaluated the impact of I38T on the fitness of a contemporary influenza A(H3N2) virus. Influenza A/Switzerland/9715293/2013 (H3N2) wild-type (WT) virus and its I38T mutant were rescued by reverse genetics. Replication kinetics were compared using ST6Gall-MDCK and A549 cells and infectivity/contact transmissibility were evaluated in guinea pigs. Nasal wash (NW) viral titres were determined by TCID₅₀ ml⁻¹ in ST6Gall-MDCK cells. Competition experiments were performed and the evolution of viral population was assessed by droplet digital RT-PCR. I38T did not alter *in vitro* replication. I38T induced comparable titres vs the WT in guinea pigs NWs and the two viruses transmitted equally by direct contact. However, a 50%:50% mixture inoculum evolved to mean WT/I38T ratios of 71%:29% and 66.4%:33.6% on days 4 and 6 p.i., respectively. Contemporary influenza A(H3N2)-I38T PA variants may conserve a significant level of viral fitness.

INTRODUCTION

Influenza viruses are among the most important pathogens causing severe respiratory tract infections. During seasonal epidemics, viruses from the A(H3N2) subtype are usually associated with increased mortality and morbidity compared to influenza A(H1N1) and influenza B strains [1]. Antigenic drifts that occur at regular intervals in influenza A(H3N2) viruses, mainly involving the B antigenic site, may result in a significant decrease in influenza vaccine effectiveness [2]. Antivirals constitute another important option for the control of seasonal influenza epidemics and pandemics [3]. Neuraminidase (NA) inhibitors (NAIs) including oseltamivir, zanamivir, peramivir and laninamivir have been first line agents since 2000 [4].

Because of their highly conserved structure among different types/subtypes and their critical role in the transcription/replication process, the polymerase acidic (PA) and the polymerase basic (PB1 and PB2) proteins have also been considered as promising targets for the development of highly potent anti-influenza drugs [5]. Baloxavir marboxil (BXM; S-033188) has been licensed in Japan, in the USA and in several other countries for the treatment of uncomplicated influenza A and B virus infections [6, 7]. Its active form, baloxavir acid (BXA; S-033447), potently inhibits the

cap-dependent endonuclease, preventing viral transcription and ultimately viral replication [8]. In clinical trials, treatment with BXM significantly improved the time to influenza symptom alleviation compared with placebo [9]. Furthermore, it reduced virus shedding more rapidly than oseltamivir, the standard of care, in otherwise healthy (CAPSTONE-1) and high-risk (CAPSTONE-2) patients [9, 10].

Amino acid substitutions at residue I38 of the PA protein have been identified as a major pathway for BXM resistance. In phase II and III clinical trials, I38T/M/F PA substitutions were detected from patients who were treated with BXM at rates that were higher for A(H3N2) viruses (9.7%) than A(H1N1)pdm09 isolates (2.2%) [9]. Furthermore, in a paediatric study, I38T/M substitutions emerged in 18/77 (23.4%) of influenza A(H3N2) viruses [11]. Influenza A(H1N1)pdm09 and A(H3N2) viruses carrying different substitutions at the I38 codon could also be readily selected by serial *in vitro* passages in presence of BXA [8, 12]. Noteworthy, the I38T is the most common PA substitution that emerged during BXM treatment in Japan and US [11, 13, 14]. Such variant displays the highest levels of reduced susceptibility to BXA (30- to 50-fold) [8, 9, 15]. Of importance, surveillance studies

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Abbreviations: BXA, baloxavir acid; BXM, baloxavir marboxil; NA, neuraminidase; PA, polymerase acidic; PB, polymerase basic.

Three supplementary figures are available with the online version of this article.

Fig. 1. *In vitro* replicative capacity of recombinant A(H3N2) viruses. Confluent ST6Gall-MDCK or A549 cells were infected with the recombinant wild-type (WT) A(H3N2) virus and the I38T mutant at a multiplicity of infection (MOI) of 0.0001 PFU per cell. Supernatants were harvested at 12, 24, 48, 72 and 96 h post-infection (p.i) and viral titres were determined in triplicate by TCID₅₀ ml⁻¹ (a) or by qPCR quantification of viral RNA (b, c). Viral titres were compared using the unpaired *t*-test with Welch's correction.

conducted in Japan during the 2018–2019 season reported that I38T variants were isolated from hospitalized children who had not received BXM treatment, suggesting the possibility of person-to-person transmission of I38T variants [16, 17].

We and others previously characterized the fitness of A(H3N2) variants in mice [18, 19]. Other authors described the impact of I38T in ferrets [12, 19, 20]. The guinea pig model provides another cost affordable option to evaluate infectivity and transmissibility of influenza viruses [21]. Such model has not been used in the context of influenza A(H3N2) resistance to baloxavir. Herein, we seek to investigate the impact of I38T on the infectivity/contact transmissibility in a seasonal influenza A(H3N2) background.

METHODS

The recombinant wild-type (WT) influenza A/Switzerland/9715293/2013 (H3N2) virus and its I38T variant were rescued by reverse genetics and polymerase chain reaction (PCR)-mediated mutagenesis, as previously described [22]. Of note, unlike the mouse-adapted variant used in the previous paper by Checkmahomed *et al.* [18], the backbone used in this study is that of the virus which was not passaged in mouse lungs. Replication kinetics experiments were performed in Madin-Darby canine kidney cells overexpressing the α 2,6 sialic acid receptor (ST6GallI-MDCK cells; kindly provided by Y. Kawaoka from the University of Wisconsin, Madison, WI [23]) as well as in human pulmonary A549 cells. Confluent cells, in 12-well plates,

Fig. 2. Effect of the I38T substitution on influenza A(H3N2) virus replication in guinea pigs. Index animals (three per group) were intranasally inoculated with 10^5 PFUs of recombinant A(H3N2) virus. Nasal washes were collected on days 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 post-infection (p.i.) and virus titres were determined in quadruplicate by $TCID_{50} \text{ ml}^{-1}$ in ST6GalI-MDCK cells. Data shown are mean \pm standard deviation. The unpaired *t*-test with Welch's correction was used for statistical comparisons. Dashed line represents the limit of detection.

were infected with the WT or I38T at a multiplicity of infection (MOI) of 0.0001 PFUs per cell (50 PFUs per well). The supernatants were harvested at 12, 24, 48, 72 and 96 h post-infection (h.p.i.) and used for quantification of viral RNA using an influenza qPCR test [24] and viral titration by $TCID_{50} \text{ ml}^{-1}$ in ST6GalI-MDCK cells.

Groups of three 6–8 week old female Hartley guinea pigs (250–300 g) (Charles River, Saint-Constant, QC, Canada), housed in individual cages, were anesthetized by isoflurane and received an intranasal inoculum of 10^5 PFUs in a total volume of 250 μl (125 μl per nostril) of the recombinant A(H3N2) WT or its I38T variant. Nasal wash samples were collected from inoculated animals at days 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 days p.i. and used to determine viral titres by $TCID_{50} \text{ ml}^{-1}$ in ST6GalI-MDCK cells.

To evaluate direct contact transmissibility, inoculated-contact animal pairs were established by placing a naïve guinea pig into each cage 24 h after inoculation of the index animal. Nasal washes samples were collected from contact animals at days 2, 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 p.i. as described for the index guinea pig.

Serum samples were collected from each index/contact animal at days 0 and 14 p.i. to evaluate specific antibody levels against the A/Switzerland/9715293/2013 (H3N2) virus using standard HA inhibition (HAI) assays [25].

Viral PA, PB1, and PB2 genes were amplified by reverse transcription (RT)-PCR from nasal washes collected from animals

Table 1. Serological status of influenza A(H3N2)-infected guinea pigs by hemagglutination inhibition (HAI) assay

Guinea pig #	Day 0	Day 14
Index WT-1	<10	80
Index WT-2	<10	80
Index WT-3	<10	80
Index I38T-1	<10	80
Index I38T-2	<10	40
Index I38T-3	<10	40
Contact WT-1	<10	20
Contact WT-2	<10	10
Contact WT-3	<10	10
Contact I38T-1	<10	20
Contact I38T-2	<10	10
Contact I38T-3	<10	10

HAI titres in serum samples collected from guinea pigs, prior to influenza A(H3N2) inoculation (day 0) and on day 14 post-inoculation, were determined by HA inhibition assays using turkey red blood cells.

at day 6 p.i. and sequenced using the ABI 3730 DNA Analyser (Applied Biosystems, Carlsbad, CA).

To gain further insight into replicative fitness of the I38T substitution, a growth-competition experiment was performed in guinea pigs. To this end, 10^5 PFUs of a 50%:50% viral mixture that consisted of 5×10^4 PFUs of the recombinant WT and 5×10^4 PFUs of its I38T counterpart was used to infect a group of three animals. Each infected animal was placed individually in a cage and nasal washes were collected as indicated above to determine the evolution of the viral proportion by using droplet digital RT-PCR (RT-ddPCR) as previously described [18, 26]. Briefly, viral RNA from nasal washes collected at days 4 and 6 p.i. was used in the RT-ddPCR workflow and data analyses were performed to assess the presence of I38T substitution with the One-Step RT-ddPCR Advanced Supermix (Bio-Rad Laboratories, Mississauga, ON, Canada) according to the manufacturer's instructions.

All animal procedures were performed in a biocontainment level two facility and approved by the Institutional Animal Care Committee of Laval University according to the guidelines of the Canadian Council on Animal Care.

Statistics

Viral titres from *in vitro* replication kinetics experiments and viral RNA copies were compared using the unpaired *t*-test with Welch's correction. Viral titres from nasal washes of guinea pigs were compared by one-way ANOVA analysis of variance, with the Dunnett's multiple comparison post-test.

Fig. 3. Transmissibility of WT and I38T influenza A(H3N2) viruses in guinea pigs. Index animals ($N=3$ per group) were inoculated with 10^5 PFUs per animal of recombinant A(H3N2) viruses. Twenty-four hours later, naïve and index animals ($N=3$ per group) were placed together into a standard guinea pig cage allowing transmission by direct contact. Nasal wash samples were collected from contact animals at days 2, 3, 5, 7, 9, and 11 post-infection (p.i.) and used to determine viral titres in quadruplicate by TCID₅₀ ml⁻¹ in ST6Gall-MDCK cells. Dashed line represents the limit of detection.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Similar replication kinetics for the WT and I38T A(H3N2) recombinants, *in vitro*

In replication kinetics experiments using ST6Gall-MDCK cells, the recombinant I38T mutant virus reached titres comparable to the respective WT virus based on TCID₅₀ ml⁻¹ assay (Fig. 1a). When tested by qPCR assays, recombinant WT and I38T viruses also followed similar replication kinetics where mean viral load peaked at 48 h p.i. reaching 3.95×10^9 and 1.91×10^9 copies ml⁻¹ for the WT and I38T, respectively (Fig. 1b). Comparable viral titres between the two recombinants were also observed for the remaining time points. The recombinant WT and I38T viruses grew at lower titres in A549 vs ST6Gall-MDCK cells. Again, the two viruses had similar replication kinetics in this cell line with viral titres peaking at 48 h p.i. reaching 1.37×10^5 and 3.46×10^5 copies ml⁻¹ for the WT and I38T, respectively (Fig. 1c). Of note, viral titres based on plaque could not be reliably determined in this cell line. This suggests that the I38T substitution does not exert a detrimental effect on replication kinetics of this A(H3N2) virus, *in vitro*. Of note, such findings are in line with previous experiments using a recombinant mouse-adapted A(H3N2) virus by our group [18] and a study characterizing clinical WT and I38T variants in MucilAir human nasal epithelial cells [27]. Moreover, Imai *et al.* [19], also reported that seasonal A(H3N2) viruses harbouring the I38T substitution, isolated from patients, grew as efficiently as their sensitive (WT) counterpart in humanized MDCK cells (hCK cells), which

express high levels of $\alpha 2,6$ -sialoglycans [28]. By contrast, other studies reported that viral growth of A(H3N2) recombinant viruses (A/Victoria/3/1975 and A/Texas/71/2017) or a clinical A/Bangladesh/3007/2017 isolate, harbouring the I38T PA substitution, were attenuated compared to the WT virus in cell culture experiments [12, 15, 20]. In conclusion, the fitness of I38T viruses, *in vitro* appears to vary depending on the viral background and/or supportive cell lines.

The WT and I38T A(H3N2) recombinants showed comparable infectivity and efficiently transmitted to contact guinea pigs with a marginal superiority of the WT in competition experiments.

The clinical impact of baloxavir-resistant infections could not be clearly established from phase three clinical trials. While the data from the CAPSTONE-1 showed that I38T/S/F variants were associated with prolonged virus shedding [13], the CAPSTONE-2 trial suggested that high-risk patients infected with I38T/S/F viruses had faster resolution of symptoms compared to infections with sensitive (WT) viruses [10]. Therefore, experimental studies of baloxavir-resistant influenza viruses using appropriate animal models could generate valuable informations in response to the public health concern regarding the replication/transmissibility of baloxavir-resistant viruses and their potential spread in the community.

Compared to ferrets, the gold standard for influenza infection/transmission studies, guinea pigs are relatively small, inexpensive, and seronegative guinea pigs are easily obtained. Furthermore, guinea pigs are highly susceptible to infection with seasonal influenza A and B viruses without prior viral adaptation through serial passage [29]. For these reasons, we sought to use the guinea pig as an alternative animal model to evaluate the replication and contact transmission of the I38T variant. To our knowledge, this study is the first to use this model for investigating the impact of the I38T substitution on contemporary influenza A(H3N2) infectivity and transmissibility using both single and competition experiments. The results described below were obtained from one of two independent experiments that generally led to the same conclusion. The results of the second experiment are summarized in the supplementary material (Figs S1–S3, available in the online version of this article).

To assess whether the I38T substitution alters virus infectivity, the nasal viral titres from WT- and I38T-infected groups were determined at different days p.i. All infected animals shed the virus between days 1 and 8 p.i. (Fig. 2). Index guinea pigs inoculated with the WT and the I38T mutant had similar mean viral titres, ranging from $10^{5.86}$ and $10^{6.03}$ on day 1, to $10^{3.28}$ and $10^{2.95}$ on day 8 p.i., respectively. Evidence for seroconversion in all WT and I38T index guinea pigs was sought by HA inhibition assays with HAI titres of 40–80 at day 14 vs <10 for pre-infected animals (Table 1). Our previous report [18] showed that recombinant A(H3N2) WT and the I38T viruses induced comparable lung viral titres in C57/BL6 mice. In addition, Chesnokov and colleagues [12], also reported that ferrets shed WT and I38T viruses for seven consecutive

Fig. 4. Competition experiments. Proportions of virus populations in the nasal washes of infected guinea pigs. Groups of animals ($N=3$ per group) were inoculated with 10^5 PFUs containing wild-type (WT) and I38T viruses either with pure virus (100%WT or mutant) or mixed at a ratio of 50%:50% (WT: I38T), based on PFU numbers. Nasal washes were collected on days 4 and 6 post-infection (p.i.), and proportion of the respective populations was determined by droplet digital reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (c).

days with no substantial differences in nasal wash viral titres between the two viruses. More recently, an Australian group reported that the clinical A(H3N2) I38T variant, recovered after baloxavir therapy, demonstrated at least three successive transmissions in a direct contact ferret experiment [27]. Imai and collaborators [19] also demonstrated that clinical A(H3N2) viruses containing the I38T substitution were as fit as the WT counterpart in hamster and mouse models. No significant difference in lung viral titres, nasal turbinates and trachea could be observed between the WT and the I38T viruses in those experiments. Thus, the I38T substitution does not impact infectivity in various animal models.

We also tested the ability of the I38T variant to transmit by direct contact between guinea pigs. The infection status of each contact animal was then assessed by determining nasal wash titres at 48 h intervals. The results indicate that the WT and I38T viruses were detected in 100% of contact recipients between days 2 and 7 p.i. with mean viral titres ranging from $10^{3.45}$ to $10^{2.45}$ TCID₅₀ ml⁻¹ for the WT and from $10^{3.2}$ to $10^{2.45}$ TCID₅₀ ml⁻¹ for the mutant (Fig. 3). These data suggest that the I38T variant could be transmitted by direct contact similar to the WT control virus. HAI titres increased from ≤ 10 (day 0) to 10–20 (day 14) (Table 1). Similar results were found in a separate experiment except for higher viral titres in WT index animals on day 4 (Figs S1 and S2).

Overall, we found that the transmission of the I38T mutant was not impaired in guinea pigs. Such findings are in accordance with recent reports assessing the impact of the I38T substitution on transmission of A(H3N2) isolates in ferrets

[19, 20]. These observations demonstrate the possibility of human-to-human transmission of the I38T substitution, which is in line with detection of the mutant in clinical surveillance studies [16, 17].

In competition experiments, we used a 50%:50% WT:I38T ratio based on PFU counts. This ratio was equivalent to 49.3%:50.7% when using RT-ddPCR quantification (Fig. 4). The proportion of the I38T population decreased to 29% (a mean ratio of 20%, 35.6 and 31%) and 33.6% (a mean ratio of 32.5%, 17 and 51%) on days 4 and 6 p.i., respectively (Fig. 4). Similar data were obtained in a separate experiment (supplementary figure 3). Overall, these observations suggest that the I38T substitution exerts some fitness alteration in the recombinant contemporary A(H3N2) virus *in vivo*. Similarly, Chesnokov and colleagues [12], also reported that the A(H3N2) WT virus had better fitness over the I38T counterpart at different competitive ratios: 10%:90%, 30%:70%, or 70%:30% in the ferret model. Taken together both the guinea pig and ferret models, the I38T substitution seems to be associated with some alteration in viral fitness. However, in a mouse co-infection model, our group reported that initial 58%:42% (WT/I38T) mixture evolved to 45%:55 and 46%: 54% on days 3 and 6 p.i. indicating that I38T variant had similar or greater fitness relative to the control virus [18]. This discrepancy is most likely due to the different genetic backgrounds and animal models in which the I38T substitution was evaluated.

Interestingly, no genotypic changes were observed in animals infected with 100% WT or 100% I38T viruses, suggesting that the I38T substitution was stable in the guinea pig model. Sequencing of viral PA, PB1, and PB2 genes from nasal wash samples confirmed the presence of the I38T substitution in the mutant virus with no additional changes.

CONCLUSION

In summary, we analysed the replicative fitness of a contemporary A(H3N2) virus with the I38T substitution *in vitro*, using different cell lines and demonstrated the conserved replicative capacity for the baloxavir-resistant I38T A(H3N2) mutant. In addition, we confirmed the feasibility of using the guinea pig model to assess the infectivity and transmissibility of such variant which would be more relevant to predict the clinical impact of this mutation. We demonstrated that conserved *in vitro* fitness of the I38T variant was correlated with a transmissibility by contact route that was equivalent to that of the WT. One limitation of our study is that we did not perform droplet transmission experiments. Thus, the risk of dissemination of the I38T mutant from treated patient to naive people could be a matter of concern. Indeed, such mutant has been already detected in patients without BXM exposure suggesting efficient transmission [16, 17].

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest

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